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SECONDARY EDUCATION AND CAPACITY BUILDING FOR SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN A DEPRESSED ECONOMY

Barakatu Abdullahi (Ph.D) barakatuav@gmail.com

GSM NO: 08034476765

Department of Educational Foundations

Faculty of Education,

Federal University Kashere,

P.M.B. 0182, Gombe State

AND

Sakina Hamza Soye

NOU212070690

AND

Adamu Abubakar

Shari'a Court of Appeal

Bauchi State Judiciary

Abstract

Education remains an indispensable tool for effective social transformation and economic prosperity of nation, yet it remains unfortunate that this important sector has been surrounded with poor political leadership in Nigeria. Education holds the master key that unlocks a country's potentials towards national transformation and sustainable development. Using discourse analysis methodology, the paper explained the key concept of secondary education and capacity building, sustainable national development, depressed economy, education and sustainable development, secondary education and capacity building for sustainable development. It highlighted the general objectives of secondary education. The paper offers some insight on secondary education and capacity building for sustainable national development in a depressed economy. Challenges facing Nigerian secondary education in the era of depressed economy were itemized and suggestions were proffered for the way forward, some among others are; the federal government should provide the required fund in line with UNESCO budget recommendation of 26% fund to education, the state and local government assisting sufficiently and also to ensure proper management of the fund available, that would ensure effective implementation of the educational system. Despite financial constraints, it is essential to prioritize education and allocate sufficient resources to ensure its continuity and quality. Education should be seen as a critical investment in human capital, as it equips the individuals with the skills and knowledge needed for future economic growth. Targeted Resource Allocation: In a depressed economy, it is crucial to allocate resources strategically, focusing on areas that yield the highest returns. This may involve directing investments towards programs that promote vocational training, entrepreneurship, and workforce development.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Capacity Building, Sustainable National Development and Depressed Economy

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Introduction

Education is recognized as a process by which human beings and societies can reach their fullest potentials. Education is a critical factor for promoting sustainable development and improving the capacity of the people to address the environment and development issues. Hence the developed countries has been making huge investment in accessing quality education in deference to United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) minimum standard of 26 per cent (%) annual budget as their mantra and swansong. It is for this coupled with responsible capacity building for secondary school teachers that developed countries occupies high ranking in United Nations Development Programmed (UNDP). Human Development Index (HDI) and UNESCO Global Mentoring Report (GMR).

No Nation can develop without a massive investment in the educational system. This is because a country's development is tied to the quality of its human resources which is the most important and critical factor of production and development. The neglect and under funding of education in Nigeria and the consequent decaying in the public secondary schools system have leading to a huge disconnection between education theory and practice and the upsurge in the number of private schools where children of the rich are educated. While the rich sends their children to school in Europe and America, the vast majority of the poor are left to attend public secondary schools According to Mordi (2008) in the education system

where the private schools are expected to play a significant role in education it is necessary for government to set good examples for the others to follow by making sure the public schools are well funded with conducive learning environment, adequate facilities and an attractive remuneration for the teachers to teach the cultural relevant curriculum that reflects the need of the society.

Education is the basic tool for development and an important end in itself. It is fundamental for the broader nation to expand human capabilities which is a pivot of development. Also education plays a key role in the ability of a developing country for self-sustaining growth and development. Todaro and Smith (2019), Education can be conceived as the development of the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains and the abilities of an individual for optimal function and performance in the society. The individual has to be helped to maximize his mental, emotional and psychological abilities that will be a benefit to him and the society in which he lives. Implicit in this is the existence of teaching, learning and training activities meant to impact information, knowledge, skills and competencies for the individual and societal improvement and development. Okeke (2018) posited that the essence of education is the harmonious development of the individual's physical, mental, spiritual and social powers that enables him to be equipped to offer useful service to God and humanity. It is to say that "education is the acquisition of knowledge, the aggregate of all processes

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through which a person develop ability, skills, attitude and other forms of behaviour with positive values in the society in which he lives. It is a lifelong process which frees a man from ignorance and superstitions. Education enhances the quality of an individual and enables him to build up his personality in such a way that he is able to play an effective role in the development of the society in which he lives (Okeke, 2018).

Conceptual Clarification of Key Concepts

It is pertinent to make clarifications of important concepts that would enhance the understanding of issues raised in this paper. These concepts are Secondary Education, Capacity Building, Sustainable National Development and Depressed Economy

Secondary Education and Capacity Building

Secondary education typically takes place after six years of primary education and before the higher education level, vocational education or employment. In most countries of the world secondary education is compulsory, and at the age of 16. Children enroll into lower secondary school around the age of twelve (12) years. Secondary education is a crucial tier in the hierarchy of education in Nigeria. It is the midway between primary and tertiary school level. It is the form of education that students receive after primary education and or before their tertiary education. It is intended for students between the ages of eleven to seventeen (11 to 17).

On the other hand, capacity Building is the improvement in the individuals or organizations to produce, perform or deploy. Capacity building for secondary school teachers is essential to enhance their knowledge, skills, and instructional practices, which ultimately leads to improved student learning outcomes. Here are some strategies and interventions for capacity building, supported by relevant citations:

1. **Professional Development Programs:** Effective professional development programs provide teachers with ongoing learning opportunities to enhance their pedagogical skills and subject knowledge. Research suggests that sustained and collaborative professional development positively impacts teachers' practice and students' achievement (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Ongoing professional development that includes active learning strategies and collaboration among educators can lead to improved instructional practices (Yoon et al., 2017).
2. **Mentoring and Coaching:** Mentoring and coaching programs provide individualized support and guidance to teachers. These approaches have been found to contribute to improved classroom practices and teacher efficacy (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). A study by Huling-Austin and Kopp (2019) highlighted that mentoring programs, when designed effectively, have a

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positive impact on teachers' knowledge and instructional strategies.

3. **Communities of Practice:**

Communities of practice create supportive networks among teachers, allowing them to share experiences, resources, and best practices. Engaging in collaborative learning communities has been shown to positively influence teachers' knowledge, classroom practice, and student achievement (Wenger, 1998; Vescio et al., 2007).

4. **Action Research:**

Encouraging teachers to engage in action research, where they systematically study and reflect on their own teaching practice which foster continuous improvement. Action research has been found to enhance teacher learning, instructional strategies, and student outcomes (Cochran-Smith and Lytle, 2023).

5. **Technology Integration:**

Equipping teachers with the skills in integrating technology into their teaching practices can enhance engagement and promote 21st-century skills among students. Research has shown that well-designed technology-enhanced professional development programs positively influences teachers' technology skills and instructional practices (Niess, 2019 and Voogt, 2011).

6. **Collaboration and Peer Learning:**

Encouraging collaboration and peer learning opportunities among

teachers can facilitate the sharing of expertise and the exchange of ideas. Collaborative professional development has been found to positively impact teachers' knowledge, instructional practices, and students' achievement (Borko and Putnam, 1995).

7. **Evaluation and Feedback:**

Providing timely and constructive feedback through classroom observations and evaluations supports teachers' professional growth. Research indicates that effective performance feedback, when coupled with targeted professional development, can lead to improved teaching practices (Garet, 2016 and Taylor, 2018).

Fuel subsidy removal is a policy decision made by governments to eliminate or reduce subsidization on the prices of petroleum products, particularly gasoline (petrol) and diesel. It involves the government removing the financial support provided to keep fuel prices artificially low in the domestic market.

Sustainable National Development

Development is the ability of society to achieve a rapid and sustained rise in the output of all gainful economic ventures. Emphasis is placed on only how society could increase output in its tangible forms (Onunwa, 1997). Development is an eclectic paradigm of social change aimed at improving the condition and quality of life of people, especially that of the majority of the poor and vulnerable people in the society. For

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development to be meaning full it has to be sustainable which is continue for a very long time without causing damage to the environment, to benefit the present and the future generations.

The concept of sustainable development was described by the (1987) brunt land commission report as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs”. Sustainability is paradigm for thinking about a future in which environment, social and economic considerations are balanced in the pursuit of development and an improved quality of life. These three spheres society, environment and economy rely on a healthy environment to provide food and resources, safe drinking water and clean air for it citizens.

Sustainable development refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it, for instance, education and training, sustainable agriculture and forestry, sustainable production and consumption, good government, research and technology (UNESCO, 2012). Sustainable development includes a number of topics which are connected to education, environment, social, economic and political roots. These topics are complex and are often difficult to define as well as find solution for. They include; reducing poverty, changing consumption patterns, global population growth and protecting human health all of which constitutes challenges to social and economic growth of the nation.

Depressed Economy

A depressed economy refers to a prolonged period of economic decline, characterized by low or negative growth rates, high levels of unemployment, reduced consumer spending, and overall economic stagnation. It can be caused by various factors such as financial crises, policy failures, external shocks, or structural imbalances within the economy. In a depressed economy, the management of sectors such as education becomes even more crucial as they play a significant role in driving economic recovery and development. Specifically, effective management of the education sector can contribute to mitigating the negative impacts of economic depression and promoting sustainable national development.

Education and Sustainable Development

Education is a key to any sustainable development program, it is recognized as a process by which human beings and societies can reach their fullest potentials. Education is a critical factor for promoting sustainable development and improving the capacity of the people to address the environment and development issues (UNICEF, 2018 Agenda 21. Education is an essential ingredient for a more sustainable future. For example it is through education that, the next generation of citizens, voters, workers, professional and leaders are prepared for life-long learning. Without education, progress towards a more sustainable future will be compromised.

Secondary Education and Capacity Building for Sustainable Development

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Secondary education typically refers to the educational level that follows after primary education level and precedes tertiary education. It usually covers the ages of twelve to eighteen (12 to 18), and its primary aim is to provide students with a broader and more in-depth knowledge base other than what was imparted during primary education (UNESCO, 2005). Secondary education plays a crucial role in preparing students for higher education, equipping them with specialized knowledge and skills, and facilitating their transition into adulthood and the workforce (World Bank, 2005). Ensuring the quality and equity of secondary education is essential for promoting inclusive and effective learning environments for all students, regardless of their backgrounds or circumstances (UNICEF, 2018).

Secondary education is a crucial period in a child's learning journey during which a learner's character, career, aspirations and readiness to take on responsibilities are shaped. Hence quality secondary education is vital for creating a bright future for individual and the nation. Jhingan (2007) posited that sustainable development means development should "keep going". It emphasizes the creation of sustainable improvement in the quality of life of people through increases in real income per capital, improvements in education, health and general quality of life and improvements in quality of national environmental resources. At the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environmental and Development (UNCED), or the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil the role of education in promoting sustainable

development was made explicit by Agenda 21 the global action plan for the 21st century (UNCED, 1992). Secondary Education is the foundational education that is available to everyone within the stipulated age limits, and also not restricted to any particular gender, place and time and upon which all other educational strata rests. Secondary education is a type of schooling which comprises six years in the primary school and three years of junior secondary and three years of senior secondary level of education. According to the National Policy on Education (2016) secondary education shall be free and compulsory. It shall include adult and non – formal education program at primary, junior and senior secondary and out of school children.

The constitution of Nigeria gives all citizens the right to education yet the delivery of education has suffered from years of neglect, compounded by inadequate attention to policy frameworks within the sectors. Funding from ongoing educational sector analysis confirm the poor state of education in Nigeria. The national literacy rate is currently 57 per cent while some 49 per cent of the teaching forces is unqualified. There is an acute shortage of infrastructure and facilities at all levels of education. Access to basic education is inhibited by gender issues and socio-cultural beliefs and practices among others (NPC, 2016). There is wide disparities that persist in educational standards and learning achievements. The system emphasizes theoretical knowledge at the expense of technical and vocational and entrepreneurial education. Schools curricula

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need urgent review to ensure that they are relevant and practice oriented (NPC, 2016). Okeke (2008) noted that the entire educational system has been bedeviled by a myriad of problems and the situation is worsening day by day. These man made problems to include; poor funding, shortage of quality staff, dearth need of infrastructure, inadequate classrooms and offices for teaching and research, shortage of books and journals, indiscipline, corruption at high and low places, cultism, irregular payment of salaries, examinations malpractices, embezzlement of fund, low staff – students ratios, poor records keeping, fraud and deception with regards to accreditations, infringements of institutional autonomy and freedom and disharmony among unions, failure to send staff regularly on capacity building courses to improve and enhances their competencies and the fact that the government often reneges on the manual agreements between it and the unions of educational institutions.

General Objectives of Secondary Education

Secondary school education has two basic components; the junior component is both pre-vocational and academic while the senior school component is more comprehensive with a core curriculum designed to broaden students' knowledge and outlook. In 1969, the National Curriculum Conference ushered in the 1977 National Policy on Education which geared towards the restoration of nation's cultural heritage. Thus the broad aims of secondary education as contained in the policy are:

1. Preparation of citizens for useful living within the society and,
2. Preparation of individuals for higher education.

These objectives are quite ideal and they require efforts and commitment on the part of all the stakeholders to ensure that secondary education succeed. However, it is observed that, there are contemporary challenges and issues negatively affecting the management of senior secondary schools education which may pose some difficulties to access the smooth running of the program. In December (2002), the United Nations general assembly adopted resolution 57/254 to put in place a United Nations decade of education for sustainable development (DESD) spanning the year 2005 to 2014 with the United Nations' Education Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as the lead agency for the decade.

The political development adopted at the world summit in sustainable development United Nations (2002) World Summit on Sustainable Development, (WSSD, 2002) states that sustainable development is built on three “interdependent and mutually reinforcing pillars “ economic growth, social development and environmental protection and sustainability which must be established at local, national, regional and global solidarity, environmental protection, democracy, health, biological and landscape diversity, climate change, gender empowerment and equity, protection of indigenous cultures. The role of education for sustainable development (ESD) is to help

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people develop the attitudes, skills and knowledge to make informed decisions for the benefit of themselves and others, now and for the future and to act upon those decisions.

Challenges of Sustainable National Development and Capacity Building in a Depressed Economy

The core challenges of education for sustainable national development and capacity building in a depressed economy is the existing policy frame work which cannot adequately support education in a global economy due to the following reasons;

1. The core principles and reasons behind policies are not sufficiently transparent
2. Education is not adequately funded due to scarce resource and inadequate private partnership in funding education. As a result teachers' condition of service is not good and motivating enough to make them undertake heavier task of preparing students for an entirely new world.
3. Educational infrastructure such as access roads, classrooms, laboratories and so on are in poor condition due to depressed economy of the country. Thus the current learning environment cannot meet the demand of 21st century learning.
4. Teachers are inadequately trained and are not regularly given room for capacity building on the job.

Educators preparation programmes in Nigeria are not yet preparing their graduates

to possess teachers and assess 21st century knowledge and skills. As a result, they cannot become change agents for embedding 21st century knowledge and skills in core subjects. There is continuous brain drain to rich and low performing institutions due to lack of capacity building for teachers on the job possibly due to depressed economy.

Conclusion

The general goals of education which is to raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under the broad national goals and live as good citizens as well as prepare the individuals for higher education cannot be achieved without effective policy implementation of reforms at the grass root level. The nine years primary/junior secondary education in the context of the national policy of education and national action plan (2006) is both prevocational and academic. This education shall be tuition free, compulsory and shall teach subjects which will enable pupils to acquire further knowledge and skills more especially if policy implementation process is effective.

Way Forward

Driving Nigeria's sustainable development in the depressed economy demands educational excellence in order for the Nigerian secondary schools education to reach the

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level of excellence required to re invigorate the Nigerian economy and improve its capacity building. The following suggestions are however made from the paper:

1. **Aligning education with emerging industries and job market needs.**
Prioritizing Education: Despite financial constraints, it is essential to prioritize education and allocate sufficient resources to ensure its continuity and quality. Education should be seen as a critical investment in human capital, as it equips individuals with the skills and knowledge needed for future economic growth.
2. **Targeted Resource Allocation:** In a depressed economy, it is crucial to allocate resources strategically, focusing on areas that yield the highest returns. This may involve directing investments towards programs that promote vocational training, entrepreneurship, and workforce development.
3. **Emphasizing Efficiency and Cost-effectiveness:** Efficiency gains and cost-saving measures should be emphasized in the management of education. This can be achieved through effective utilization of existing infrastructure, optimizing staffing levels, leveraging technology for remote learning and administrative processes, and promoting public-private partnerships.
4. **Enhancing Access and Equity:** In times of economic crisis, ensuring equal access to education becomes more vital as vulnerable populations may face additional barriers. Efforts should be made to provide equitable opportunities for education, including scholarships, subsidies, and targeted interventions to support disadvantaged students.
5. **Collaboration and Innovation:** Collaboration between government, educational institutions, private sector, and civil society is essential in overcoming the challenges posed by a depressed economy. Stakeholders can collaborate to develop innovative solutions, explore alternative funding mechanisms, and establish partnerships to enhance the quality and relevance of education.
6. **Continuous Professional Development:** Investing in the professional development of educators and administrators becomes even more crucial during economic downturns. Providing opportunities for continuous learning, training, and skill enhancement can ensure that the education sector remains resilient and adaptable to changing circumstances.
7. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regular monitoring and evaluation of educational programs and initiatives are essential to assess their effectiveness and make informed decisions. Data-driven approaches can help identify areas of

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improvement and inform evidence-based policy-making in the education sector.

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Vescio, V., et al. (2007). A review of research on the impact of professional learning communities on Sustainable national development refers to the long-term economic, social, and environmental progress of a country while preserving and protecting natural resources and the well-being of its citizens. It involves implementing policies, strategies, and practices that promote inclusive growth, environmental sustainability, social equity, and good governance.

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